

Molecular Dynamics of Formyl Chloride

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The kinetic constants method has been applied to the case of planar *AXYZ* type molecules to evaluate the molecular constants such as potential energy constants, vibrational mean amplitudes, Coriolis coupling constants and centrifugal distortion constants. The values so obtained seem to be reasonable. A close fit of the calculated values of the centrifugal distortion constants with the corresponding observed values bring out the significance of the new procedure involving kinetic constants.

THE kinetic constants method has been applied by Mohan *et al.*¹⁻⁵ to obtain acceptable sets of potential constants in different types of polyatomic molecules. These constants in turn have led to significant results of molecular constants. The good agreement between the calculated values and the observed values (wherever available) has established the merits of the procedure. Such initial studies were confined to 2×2, 3×3 and 4×4 vibrational problems. The present paper is an example of the higher order 5×5 vibrational problem.

The purpose of the present paper is to adopt the procedure of kinetic constants in the evaluation of the potential constants and other molecular constants of *AXYZ* planar type molecules (formyl chloride and its isotopes), which involve 5×5 vibrational problems. The secular equation has been solved in a highly sophisticated manner.

Theoretical considerations: *AXYZ* molecule belongs to the *C_s* symmetry and hence the fundamental frequencies are 5*A'* + 1*A''*, where *A''* represents an out-of-plane vibration. The symmetry coordinates used here are given below.

$$A' \text{ species: } S_1 = \Delta d_1$$

$$S_2 = 2^{-\frac{1}{2}} (\Delta d_2 + \Delta d_3)$$

$$S_3 = 2^{-\frac{1}{2}} (\Delta d_2 - \Delta d_3)$$

$$S_4 = 6^{-\frac{1}{2}} (\Delta \alpha + \Delta \gamma - 2\Delta \beta)$$

$$S_5 = 2^{-\frac{1}{2}} (\Delta \alpha - \Delta \gamma)$$

$$A'' \text{ species: } S_6 = \Delta \delta$$

The most general quadratic potential energy function in terms of internal coordinates has been considered and hence *F*-matrix elements have been obtained, which are

A' species :

$$F_{11} = f_{\bar{a}_1}$$

$$F_{22} = (1/2) [f_{\bar{a}_2} + f_{\bar{a}_3} + 2f_{\bar{a}_2\bar{a}_3}]$$

$$F_{33} = (1/2) [f_{\bar{a}_2} + f_{\bar{a}_3} - 2f_{\bar{a}_2\bar{a}_3}]$$

$$F_{44} = (1/6) [\epsilon f_{\alpha} + 4\eta f_{\beta} + \pi f_{\gamma} - 4\sqrt{\eta\epsilon} f_{\alpha\beta} + 2\sqrt{\epsilon\pi} f_{\alpha\gamma} - 4\sqrt{\eta\pi} f_{\beta\gamma}]$$

$$F_{55} = (1/2) [\epsilon f_{\alpha} + \pi f_{\gamma} - 2\sqrt{\epsilon\pi} f_{\alpha\gamma}]$$

$$F_{12} = (1/\sqrt{2}) [f_{\bar{a}_1\bar{a}_2} + f_{\bar{a}_1\bar{a}_3}]$$

$$F_{13} = (1/\sqrt{2}) [f_{\bar{a}_1\bar{a}_2} - f_{\bar{a}_1\bar{a}_3}]$$

$$F_{14} = (1/\sqrt{6}) [\sqrt{\epsilon} f_{\bar{a}_1\alpha} - 2\sqrt{\eta} f_{\bar{a}_1\beta} + \sqrt{\pi} f_{\bar{a}_1\gamma}]$$

$$F_{15} = (1/\sqrt{2}) [\sqrt{\epsilon} f_{\bar{a}_1\alpha} - \sqrt{\pi} f_{\bar{a}_1\gamma}]$$

$$F_{23} = (1/2) [f_{\bar{a}_2} - f_{\bar{a}_3}]$$

$$F_{24} = (1/\sqrt{12}) [\sqrt{\epsilon} (f_{\bar{a}_2\alpha} + f_{\bar{a}_3\alpha}) - 2\sqrt{\eta} (f_{\bar{a}_2\beta} + f_{\bar{a}_3\beta}) + \sqrt{\pi} (f_{\bar{a}_2\gamma} + f_{\bar{a}_3\gamma})]$$

$$F_{25} = (1/2) [\sqrt{\epsilon} (f_{\bar{a}_2\alpha} + f_{\bar{a}_3\alpha}) - \sqrt{\pi} (f_{\bar{a}_2\gamma} + f_{\bar{a}_3\gamma})]$$

$$F_{34} = (1/\sqrt{2}) [\sqrt{\epsilon} (f_{\bar{a}_2\alpha} - f_{\bar{a}_3\alpha}) - 2\sqrt{\eta} (f_{\bar{a}_2\beta} - f_{\bar{a}_3\beta}) + \sqrt{\pi} (f_{\bar{a}_2\gamma} - f_{\bar{a}_3\gamma})]$$

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$$F_{23} = (1/2) [\sqrt{\epsilon} (f_{\alpha_2\alpha} - f_{\alpha_3\alpha}) - \sqrt{\pi} (f_{\alpha_2\gamma} - f_{\alpha_3\gamma})]$$

$$F_{43} = (1/\sqrt{12}) [\epsilon f_{\alpha} - \pi f_{\gamma} - 2\sqrt{\epsilon\eta} f_{\alpha\beta} + 2\sqrt{\eta\pi} f_{\beta\gamma}]$$

$$F_{66} = f_{\delta}$$

where, $\epsilon = d_1 d_2$, $\eta = d_2 d_3$ and $\pi = d_1 d_3$.

On the basis of Wilson's formula⁸, G -matrix elements have been calculated. The kinetic constants are obtained from a knowledge of G -matrix elements.

The method of kinetic constants for evaluating the force constants relates the off-diagonal elements to the diagonal elements of the F -matrix through the relation.

$$\frac{F_{ij}}{F_{jj}} = \frac{K_{ij}}{K_{jj}} [i < j; i, j = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5]$$

Thus in the determination of symmetry force constants involved in the secular equation, $n_i(n_i - 1)/2$, additional data other than n_i frequencies are supplied. The equations involving A' species are easily solved in this manner.

Compliance constants: The compliance constants are calculated for these cases by Decius method⁷.

Vibrational mean amplitudes: Utilising Cyvin's equation⁹ $\Sigma = L\Delta L'$, the symmetrised mean square amplitude quantities for both the bonded and non-bonded distances are evaluated at 298-16 K. On the basis of these values, the mean amplitudes of vibration for these molecules are evaluated.

Coriolis coupling constants: Coriolis vibration rotation constants ζ^{α} ($\alpha = x, y, z$) in this type of molecules arise from the couplings, $A' \times A''$. The Coriolis matrix elements, C_{ij}^{α} ($\alpha = x, y, z$) are obtained by the vector method of Meal and Polo⁶. The matrices are related to the C^{α} matrices as

$$\zeta^{\alpha} = L^{-1} C^{\alpha} (L^{-1})'$$

where, L is the normal coordinates transformation matrix.

Centrifugal distortion constants: Following Kivelson and Wilson¹⁰, centrifugal distortion constants of the molecules have been calculated. The $t_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}$ elements are calculated from a knowledge of the T_s matrix elements.

Results and Discussion

The structural parameters and the vibrational frequencies of the molecule under study are given

TABLE 1—MOLECULAR PARAMETERS* AND VIBRATIONAL FREQUENCIES* OF AXYZ TYPE MOLECULES

Molecule	Bond distances (Å)			Bond angle (degree)			Frequency (cm ⁻¹)					
	d_1 (C-H)	d_2 (C-O)	d_3 (C-Cl)	α (HCO)	β (OCCl)	γ (ClCH)	ν_1	ν_2	ν_3	ν_4	ν_5	ν_6
¹² CHOCI	1.094	1.184	1.768	126.85	123.30	109.85	2 929.2	1 784.1	1 307.2	738.8	458	932.1
¹³ CHOCI	1.094	1.184	1.768	126.85	123.30	109.85	2 918.4	1 745.2	1 303.4	718.6	454	919.4
¹³ CDOCl	1.094	1.184	1.768	126.85	123.30	109.85	2 215.0	1 748.5	986.2	700.4	454.4	779.3

*Ref. 14

TABLE 2—KINETIC CONSTANTS (10⁻²³ g) OF FORMYL CHLORIDE

Molecule	k_{a_1}	$k_{a_1 a_2}$	k_{α}	k_{β}	$k_{a_2 \beta}$	$k_{a_2 \gamma}$	$k_{a_1 \beta}$
	k_{a_2}	$k_{a_1 a_3}$	k_{γ}	$k_{\alpha \beta}$	$k_{a_3 \beta}$	$k_{a_3 \alpha}$	$k_{a_1 \alpha}$
	k_{a_3}	$k_{a_2 a_3}$	$k_{\alpha \gamma}$	$k_{\beta \gamma}$	$k_{a_3 \alpha}$	$k_{a_3 \gamma}$	$k_{a_1 \gamma}$
¹² CHOCI	0.166 8	0.045 8	0.125 1	0.349 9	0.379 0	-0.227 6	k_{δ} -0.047 6
	1.796 0	0.024 2	0.099 7	-0.179 9	0.432 1	-0.151 7	0.028 9
	2.589 5	1.056 8	0.050 4	-0.162 6	-0.203 7	-0.182 3	0.025 9 0.120 9
¹³ CHOCI	0.164 1	0.040 9	0.125 2	0.352 0	0.365 3	-0.161 2	-0.034 4
	1.788 5	0.020 6	0.099 6	-0.181 1	0.418 8	-0.316 0	0.020 9
	2.598 7	1.018 7	0.051 5	-0.163 5	-0.197 0	-0.177 2	0.018 7 0.115 7
¹³ CDOCl	0.321 4	0.080 6	0.147 6	0.355 8	0.367 6	-0.248 3	-0.069 1
	1.808 8	0.043 5	0.129 6	-0.173 3	0.413 3	-0.360 8	0.040 0
	2.612 9	0.998 1	0.023 2	-0.171 4	-0.164 0	-0.134 7	0.039 2 0.173 2

TABLE 3—POTENTIAL CONSTANTS (10^6 dyne cm^{-1}) OF FORMYL CHLORIDE

Molecule	$f_{\bar{a}_1}$	$f_{\bar{a}_1\bar{a}_2}$	f_{α}	f_{β}	$f_{\bar{a}_2\beta}$	$f_{\bar{a}_2\gamma}$	$f_{\bar{a}_1\beta}$
	$f_{\bar{a}_2}$	$f_{\bar{a}_1\bar{a}_3}$	f_{γ}	$f_{\alpha\beta}$	$f_{\bar{a}_3\beta}$	$f_{\bar{a}_3\alpha}$	$f_{\bar{a}_1\alpha}$
	$f_{\bar{a}_3}$	$f_{\bar{a}_2\bar{a}_3}$	$f_{\alpha\gamma}$	$f_{\beta\gamma}$	$f_{\bar{a}_2\alpha}$	$f_{\bar{a}_3\gamma}$	$f_{\bar{a}_1\gamma}$ f_{β}
$^{12}\text{CHOCI}$	3.883 7	-0.158 2	0.373 3	1.161 2	-0.614 7	0.680 4	0.159 0
	10.217 9	-0.036 1	0.238 2	-0.640 6	-0.703 2	0.465 6	-0.099 9
	5.580 4	+1.262 0	0.252 4	-0.512 9	0.776 1	0.717 7	-0.081 5 0.372 8
$^{14}\text{CHOCI}$	3.925 0	-0.154 4	0.408 9	1.288 6	-0.672 3	0.720 6	0.126 5
	10.739 4	-0.036 5	0.262 3	-0.709 8	-0.770 8	0.507 9	-0.079 7
	6.046 5	+1.587 2	0.325 3	-0.569 9	0.827 0	0.772 1	-0.666 4 0.346 7
$^{13}\text{CDOCI}$	5.430 9	-0.263 0	0.449 7	1.310 8	-0.684 0	0.753 4	0.257 3
	9.224 5	-0.093 6	0.278 7	-0.729 3	-0.768 9	0.523 6	-0.160 7
	5.548 5	+1.841 5	0.269 0	-0.575 3	0.818 5	0.741 2	-0.136 2 0.373 2

in Table 1. The kinetic constants of these cases are given in Table 2. The kinetic constant for C—H bond is in agreement with the earlier values^{11,12}. With the substitution of D , the kinetic constant is doubled. Similarly $k_{\bar{a}_2}$ and $k_{\bar{a}_3}$ for C—O and C—Cl bonds are consistent with the earlier works¹¹⁻¹³. It is important to note that the interaction kinetic constants do not show much variation.

The valence force constants are presented in Table 3. The stretching force constants $f_{\bar{a}_2}$ and $f_{\bar{a}_3}$ for C—O and C—Cl bonds do not vary appreciably for all these cases. Other interaction constants seem to be reasonable. It is pleasing to note the same sign for the angle-angle force constants $f_{\alpha\beta}$ and $f_{\beta\gamma}$, and the corresponding kinetic constants $k_{\alpha\beta}$ and $k_{\beta\gamma}$.

 TABLE 4—MEAN SQUARE AMPLITUDE (10^{-8} Å²), MEAN AMPLITUDE (Å) AND NON-BONDED MEAN SQUARE AMPLITUDE (10^{-8} Å²) AT 298-16 K

Molecule	Mean square amplitude									
	$\sigma_{\bar{a}_1}$	$\sigma_{\bar{a}_1\bar{a}_2}$	σ_{α}	σ_{β}	$\sigma_{\bar{a}_2\beta}$	$\sigma_{\bar{a}_2\gamma}$	$\sigma_{\bar{a}_1\beta}$	σ_{γ}	σ_{γ}	σ_{γ}
	$\sigma_{\bar{a}_2}$	$\sigma_{\bar{a}_1\bar{a}_3}$	σ_{γ}	$\sigma_{\alpha\beta}$	$\sigma_{\bar{a}_3\beta}$	$\sigma_{\bar{a}_3\alpha}$	$\sigma_{\bar{a}_1\alpha}$	X...Y	Y...Z	X...Z
$^{12}\text{CHOCI}$	6.241 0	-0.209 1	31.981 9	0.889 2	-0.607 2	1.292 1	0.393 5	9.344 9	1.401 1	14.307 6
	2.150 3	-0.253 8	21.234 2	0.609 8	-0.543 2	1.170 1	-0.327 4			
	0.998 6	-0.566 8	-25.607 3	0.319 6	-0.807 0	-0.392 4	-0.141 5			
$^{14}\text{CHOCI}$	5.705 2	-1.005 4	32.776 0	0.076 4	0.723 4	0.248 9	1.029 6	9.098 2	2.383 8	16.467 0
	1.532 1	-0.051 4	21.096 3	-0.606 6	0.235 9	1.068 2	-0.560 6			
	0.200 2	-0.676 5	-26.127 4	0.312 3	-1.223 6	-1.011 5	-0.612 4			
$^{13}\text{CDOCI}$	4.601 6	-0.343 7	19.609 7	0.914 0	-0.523 8	1.330 3	-0.443 6	4.945 6	3.420 3	8.028 9
	1.989 2	0.010 9	11.173 8	-1.809 4	0.263 4	1.412 3	0.378 6			
	2.092 9	-0.953 2	-14.082 7	0.394 1	-0.959 7	-1.429 5	0.151 7			
						30.272 7				
	Mean amplitude									
	$l_{\bar{a}_1}$	$l_{\bar{a}_2}$	$l_{\bar{a}_3}$	l_{β}	l_{γ}	l_{γ}				
	(C—H)	(C—O)	(C—Cl)	H...Y	Y...Z	X...Z				
$^{12}\text{CHOCI}$	0.079 0	0.046 4	0.031 6	0.096 67	0.037 43	0.119 61				
$^{14}\text{CHOCI}$	0.075 5	0.039 1	0.034 1	0.095 38	0.048 82	0.128 32				
$^{13}\text{CDOCI}$	0.067 8	0.044 6	0.045 7	0.070 33	0.058 48	0.089 60				
	0.0738 ^a		0.051 9 ^b							

^aRef. 12. ^bRef. 13.

The valence mean square amplitudes and the mean amplitudes for both bonded and non-bonded distances are listed in Table 4. The following observations are significant: (i) the mean amplitude of vibration for C—H is almost the same in $^{12}\text{CHOCI}$ and $^{13}\text{CHOCI}$, and (ii) the C—O and C—Cl mean amplitudes of vibration are nearly the same in all the three cases. The present values of vibrational mean amplitudes agree quite well with the values available in literature.

The Coriolis vibration-rotation constants of the molecules are reported in Table 5. The high values of ζ_{56} suggest that the coupling between the vibrations concerned are significant. The centrifugal distortion constants are presented in Table 6. A comparison between the calculated and the observed values is also presented in Table 6. The good agreement between them in all the cases again suggests that the method of kinetic constants leads to significant results relating to the problem of molecular vibrations.

TABLE 5—CORIOLIS COUPLING CONSTANTS

Molecule	$^{12}\text{CHOCI}$	$^{13}\text{CHOCI}$	$^{12}\text{CDOCl}$
ζ_{16}^{α}	0.049 4	0.037 7	-0.032 5
ζ_{26}^{α}	-0.352 9	0.034 5	-0.009 9
ζ_{36}^{α}	-0.342 2	-0.868 1	-0.459 4
ζ_{46}^{α}	-0.632 5	0.049 2	-0.306 7
ζ_{56}^{α}	-0.664 1	-0.568 5	-0.519 5
ζ_{16}^{ν}	-0.503 8	0.594 6	0.097 7
ζ_{26}^{ν}	-0.637 5	-0.952 7	0.702 0
ζ_{36}^{ν}	0.346 9	0.211 1	-0.137 2
ζ_{46}^{ν}	0.043 5	0.382 8	0.054 6
ζ_{56}^{ν}	0.046 6	0.001 4	-0.120 6

TABLE 6—CENTRIFUGAL DISTORTION CONSTANTS (kHz)

	$^{12}\text{CHOCI}$	$^{13}\text{CHOCI}$	$^{12}\text{CDOCl}$
D_J	3 390 7 3 669 4 ^a	3.081 4 —	2.844 0 3.415 0 ^b
D_K	3 204.1 2 788.5 ^a	2 881.4 —	1 357.7 1 096.47 ^b
D_{JK}	-65 829 8 -59 382 0 ^a	-50.811 0 —	-27.737 1 -25.796 ^b
δ_J	0.224 9 0.387 5 ^a	0.207 0 —	0.377 6 0.452 ^b

^aRef. 15 (observed values). ^bRef. 14 (observed values).

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References

1. S. MOHAN, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Belg*, 1977, 86, 531
2. S. MOHAN, *Acta Phys. Pol., A*, 1980, 57, 433.
3. S. MOHAN and S. RAJARAMAN, *Indian J. Pure Appl. Phys.*, 1982, 20, 148
4. S. MOHAN and S. GUNASEKARAN, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Fr.*, 1983, 173.
5. S. MOHAN and K. G. RAVIKUMAR, *Acta Phys. Pol., A*, 1983, 63, 77.
6. E. B. WILSON, JR., D. C. DECIUS and P. C. CROSS, "Molecular Vibrations", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1955.
7. J. C. DECIUS, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1963, 38, 241
8. S. J. CYVIN, "Molecular Vibrations and Mean Square Amplitudes", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1963.
9. J. H. MEAL and S. R. POLO, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1953, 24, 1119.
10. D. KIVELSON and E. B. WILSON, JR., *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1952, 20, 1575; 1953, 21, 1229.
11. P. THIRUGNANSAMBANDAM and G. J. SRINIVASAN, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1969, 50, 2467.
12. S. MOHAN, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci., Sect. A*, 1979, 88, 351.
13. P. THIRUGNANSAMBANDAM and S. MOHAN, *Indian J. Phys., B*, 1977, 51, 342.
14. R. W. DEVIS and M. C. L. GERRY, *J. Mol. Spectrosc.*, 1983, 97, 117.
15. M. SUZUKI, K. YAMADA and M. TAKAMI, *J. Mol. Spectrosc.*, 1981, 88, 207.